

Deliverable 3.5

Interactive Handbook: Engagement and Partnerships for Outstanding Open Science Communication

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ENJOI - ENgagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication

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www.enjoiscomm.eu

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Contributor	Description
v1.0	24.07.2023	Stickydot	First draft
v1.1	19.09.2023	Stickydot	First full-text
v1.2	22.09.2023	FCiências.ID	Revision and creation of second version
v1.3	25.09.2023	External designer	First interactive version
v1.4	18.10.2023	FCiências.ID and Stickydot	Revision and creation of final interactive version
v1.5	31.10.2023	Formicablu	Final revision and upload by the Project Coordinator

QUALITY ASSURANCE

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we arranged an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the task leader. All partners contributed and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the final version was submitted to the project coordinator for a final review and validation.

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY AND DISCLAIMER

This deliverable contains original, unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. It builds upon the experience of the team and related work published on this topic. Acknowledgement of previously published material and others' work has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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Summary

This deliverable reports on the work carried out in WP3. Specifically, it presents the results of task 3.4 “Nurturing exploitable and transferable resources” led by Stickydot (SD), in collaboration with FCIências.ID (FC.ID) and Formicablu (FB).

The main objective of this task was to showcase the co-creation methodologies developed within the project in the form of an interactive handbook. This exploitable resource aims to support and inspire other researchers and practitioners in the design and implementation of participatory workshops.

The interactive handbook, “*Engagement and Partnerships for Outstanding Open Science Communication (OOSC)*”, which is [publicly available here](#), collects the revised versions of methodologies for establishing partnerships and running Engagement Workshops (EWs) and Labs in contexts of science communication. This handbook will be also available in the ENJOI Observatory for OOSC.

Project Overview

ENJOI (*ENgagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication*) is exploring and testing engagement as a key asset of innovation in science communication distributed via media platforms, with a strong focus on journalism.

Through a combination of methodologies and in collaboration with producers, target users and stakeholders of science communication, ENJOI is co-creating and selecting a set of standards, principles and indicators (SPIs) to produce a Manifesto for Outstanding Open Science Communication (OOSC). ENJOI is deploying a series of actions via Engagement Workshops (EWs), Labs, field and participatory research, evaluation and testing phases.

ENJOI has also built an Observatory as its landmark product to make all results and outputs available to foster capacity building and collaboration of all actors in the field. The Observatory, currently hosted within the project website, will evolve into an independent product bound to remain online and actively nurtured well beyond the project end. Furthermore, the ENJOI Observatory will be integral to the COALESCE project, recently funded under the Horizon Europe scheme to build the European Competence Centre for Science Communication.

The ENJOI Observatory will provide useful insights, resources and tools to support science and generalist journalists in their work. ENJOI is working in four countries: Belgium, Italy, Portugal and Spain, considering different cultural contexts. ENJOI's ultimate goal is to improve science communication by making it more consistently reliable, truthful, open and engaging. Contextually, ENJOI will contribute to the active development of critical thinking, digital awareness and media literacy of all actors involved in the process.

ENJOI

**INTERACTIVE HANDBOOK:
ENGAGEMENT AND PARTNERSHIPS
FOR OUTSTANDING OPEN SCIENCE
COMMUNICATION**

ENJOI

- 1 Introduction**
- 2 Building a partnership**
- 3 Co-creation process**
- 4 Learnings from ENJOI**

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ABOUT THIS HANDBOOK

ENJOI set up a process to co-create a set of [standards, principles, indicators \(SPIs\)](#) and tools to improve science communication and journalism. We brought together civil society, policy makers, industries, academics, journalists and researchers as stakeholders across Italy, Spain, Portugal and Belgium over the three years of the project. By means of engagement and participation of stakeholders in the whole process of definition of SPIs and tools, we combined literature analysis, expert consultations, media landscape research, co-creation design and implementation with a variety of stakeholders.

One feature of the ENJOI co-creation process was the “cascade effect”. Each step of the process took place country by country, with time in between to share learnings and adapt the process. Some of these adaptations are highlighted in this document to show the flexibility of the methodology. We also include tips on implementation.

This handbook shares the details of the co-creation methods for anyone thinking about setting up a similar process: what can be taken from the ENJOI findings? What worked well? And what have we learned?

ABOUT ENJOI

ENJOI (ENGagement and JOurnalism Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication) explored and tested engagement as a key asset of innovation in science communication distributed via media platforms, with a strong focus on journalism.

Through a combination of methodologies and in collaboration with producers, target users and stakeholders of science communication, ENJOI co-created a set of [standards, principles, indicators \(SPIs\)](#) to produce a [Manifesto for Outstanding Open Science Communication \(OOSC\)](#).

ENJOI has also built an [Observatory](#) as its landmark product to make all results and outputs available to foster capacity building and collaboration of all actors in the field. It will be integral to the [COALESCE](#) project, building the European Competence Centre for Science Communication.

BUILDING A PARTNERSHIP

The first part of the co-creation process is to build a partnership around the topic. ENJOI built partnerships across four countries, each of which participated in the Engagement Workshops and Labs where the co-creation took place. Four ENJOI organisations, each working in their own country, brought together groups of 8-15 people working in different aspects of science communication, with a good balance of practitioners and researchers, including science and data journalists, communication and dissemination experts, citizen science practitioners, museum staff, media editors, cross-sectional experts, local activists; teachers and students and more.

The concept of the ENJOI partnerships was based on the Community of Practice (CoP) approach to social learning. A CoP is a group of people who “share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly.”

SUCCESS FACTORS

Identity: Communities of practice thrive when people feel connected to each other and the subject they're passionate about. It's crucial to clearly define what the community is all about for it to succeed.

Leadership is also vital. The community needs dedicated and skilled individuals who are willing to take charge and keep things running smoothly. Many communities fail not because people lose interest but because there's no one to handle the logistics and create a good learning environment.

Time is a challenge for most communities because members have other things to do. Even if people are interested, finding the time can be tough. To tackle this, it's essential to make sure that everyone gets something valuable in return for the time they invest in the community.

1. GAINING INTERNAL BUY-IN

2. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

3. STAKEHOLDER PRIORITISATION

4. REACHING OUT

5. COLLABORATIVE PARTNERSHIP KICK-OFF

Read more about the key barriers and solutions to building partnerships in our ENJOI report: [Developing a roadmap](#)

1. GAINING INTERNAL BUY-IN

It is crucial to the success of co-creation partnerships that the process has internal buy-in; meaning it is understood and agreed on internally, within each partner organisation. ENJOI partners held a first internal launch meeting to discuss the collaborative partnerships. The objectives of this launch meeting were:

- To engage staff in the project, beyond the individuals working directly on ENJOI
- To align on the goals of the ENJOI collaborative partnerships
- To reflect on how the organisation as a whole can benefit from the work on ENJOI

Time frame: 60 minutes

Group size: 10-25 people

Resources: Example agenda and tools in the ENJOI report [Developing a roadmap](#) p10.

Tip

Use playful warm-ups and energisers to help your team get ready to contribute. [SessionLab](#) has some good ones.

2. STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

This is a necessary step to identify the individuals that should be involved in the co-creation process, who influences them, directly or indirectly, who is affected by them and how these actors are related. ENJOI teams mapped stakeholders to identify individuals that have a stake in the issue of standards in science communication and science journalism. This was done through a short workshop plus some follow-up.

Time frame: 60 minutes

Group size: 3-8 people

Resources: [Online mapping template](#)

Adaptation

For ENJOI, in Spain, Science for Change decided to work with an asynchronous approach involving a core group of representatives from the company to develop the partnership. For that purpose, they invited three people from the company that work with science communication to use an online collaborative tool (Miro) where everyone could contribute their knowledge.

Tip

You could use the Quadruple Helix Model (see opposite) to think about how to categorise your stakeholders.

3. STAKEHOLDER PRIORITISATION

1

2

3

This exercise identifies actors that are best placed to contribute to your partnerships. It should be performed by the same group as the stakeholder mapping but it can be interesting to bring in the perspectives of other colleagues and close collaborators depending on availability as well.

Time frame: 60 minutes

Group size: 3-8 people

Resources: [Online prioritisation template](#), [Barriers-incentives table](#), [contact details table](#)

Tip

Before any prioritisation exercise, make sure the group agrees on what they are prioritising! Do they all understand things the same way?

4. REACHING OUT

From the lists of potential stakeholders supplied by your colleagues from the stakeholder prioritisation exercise, draw up shortlists for each of the stakeholder groups. These shortlists should be designed to ensure high levels of expertise and interest on the topic, a diverse range of perspectives, a balance of theorists and practitioners, a gender balance and a diverse range of cultural backgrounds. Aim to have at least six contacts in your shortlists for each of your 5-6 priority profiles. For profiles where you have insufficient shortlisted contacts, get in touch with local or national organisations that can help provide the relevant contacts. Conduct desk research to identify possible participants.

Resources: Email template

Adaptation

In ENJOI, after translating the materials into Italian, Formicablu sent individual emails, carefully personalising each message by highlighting why they decided to invite them and the added value of participating for each person. These invitations resulted in a good response from the first round.

Dear **NAME**

Following our phone conversation, I am happy to share more information about the **PROJECT NAME** project and what it would mean to be part of our partnership.

As I mentioned, **PROJECT NAME** is a project that aims to **PROJECT OBJECTIVES**. We want to co-create these recommendations and tools with practitioners in **CO-CREATION PROCESS DETAILS**.

We would really appreciate it if you or another colleague from your organisation agreed to be part of our partnership in Belgium. In practice it means **LOGISTICS DETAILS**. These workshops will take place online or in person depending on the situation and preferences of participants. Note, that travel expenses in case of in person meetings will be reimbursed.

You might ask what's in it for me so I am listing some main benefits below:

BENEFITS

If you have any questions or require more information do not hesitate to reach out. I would be grateful if you could let me know whether you would agree to become part of the partnership by **DEADLINE**.

Best regards,

NAME

5. COLLABORATIVE PARTNERSHIP KICK-OFF

This will be the first meeting for your freshly-established collaborative partnership. The objectives are:

- To introduce participants to each other, make connections between the members of the new partnership and make space for them to share their stories;
- To set a framework for cooperation where participants feel at ease to contribute, where all voices are valued equally, regardless of stakeholder profile, and where diversity is a strength to power the group's co-creation activities;
- To introduce the role of the collaborative partnership; and to incentivise participants to play an active role in the co-creation process.

Time frame: 120 minutes plus break time

Group size: 8-15 people plus host participants

Adaptation

This session can be integrated into the Engagement Workshop if needed.

Tip

This is the first time your stakeholders are meeting in person - think about how you can make the atmosphere convivial! Food, drink and time to chat are important.

Read more about the detailed steps and find more resources for building partnerships in our ENJOI report: [Developing a roadmap](#)

CO-CREATION PROCESS

In ENJOI, after each country had completed a set of engagement workshop modules, the partners met for mutual learning sessions where lessons learnt were shared. This allowed us to adapt the model, improving the dynamics from one to the next. This “cascade” model worked well in ensuring we adapted the workshop to a range of contexts.

THE ENJOI CO-DESIGN METHODOLOGY WAS MADE UP OF SIX STEPS:

A. GATHERING PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS

B. ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOP MODULE 1: CO-CREATING PRINCIPLES

C. ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOP MODULE 2: IDENTIFYING STANDARDS

D. ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOP MODULE 3: DEFINING INDICATORS AND TOOLS

E. EUROPEAN CONSENSUS WORKSHOP

F. LABS

Read more about the detailed steps in our ENJOI reports [Co-designing innovative multi-stakeholder engagement](#), our [Report on the ENJOI Engagement Workshops](#) and our [Report on the ENJOI Labs](#).

A. GATHERING PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS

How can you ensure your co-creation process takes account of the voices of the general public, in a context where it is not possible to involve the general public in your workshops?

ENJOI's first step ensured that the ENJOI co-creation process took as its starting point the views of the general public of each partnership before stakeholders came together to build on these views. Ensuring the voice of the general public is represented in the co-creation process was essential as they are a key end-user of open science communication, and science journalism in particular. ENJOI used a semi-structured interview or online survey of people resident in each country who were non-professionals in research, journalism or science communication. They ensured a range of ages, a balance of gender identities and, where relevant, a balance of linguistic communities. No personal data was collected.

Questions:

- Aligning on the topic: "If I say to you 'science communication,' what is the first thing you think about?"
- Sharing: "In what situation is it important to communicate about science research?" and "Can you give an example where that worked well?"
- Reflection: "What made it work well?"

The results were collected by local partners and analysed using a simple analysis grid to produce word clouds in both English and local languages. The analysis drew out key elements mentioned by participants in their answers to the "reflection" question in particular.

Tip

Ensure your survey questions are in plain, simple language. By asking participants to imagine a situation where science communication worked well, we encouraged them to draw on real scenarios for their responses.

B. ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOP MODULE 1: CO-CREATING PRINCIPLES

The first time a co-creation group comes together, it is important to align around the key concepts: in our case, those of science journalism and science communication and how they are perceived by the public. Our aim was to use these perceptions as a starting point to identify the key principles of outstanding open science communication.

In ENJOI, this workshop module was held in-person, and fused with the following two modules, but it could also be adapted to be held online using tools such as Miro or Mural. Participants received a pre-read with some of the ENJOI outcomes and the results of the citizen questionnaire in their country.

There were nine key steps to the module:

- 1. Welcome:** We welcomed participants, explaining the objectives, detailing the agenda and giving practical, logistical or technical guidelines. (5 minutes)
- 2. Warm-up activity** to align on the notion of open science communication and help participants get to know each other. Participants broke up into groups of three and had one minute each to briefly present themselves and say what makes great science communication for them. (10 minutes)
- 3. Presentation** of public opinion results. (10 minutes)
- 4. Structured discussion:** “What surprises you in these outcomes?” We gave participants two minutes to write sticky notes, one sticky note per feedback comment. They had time to read each other’s comments. Then we handed out sticky dots to prioritise the comments (three per participant) and asked them to prioritise the comments they agreed with. We then used the highest-prioritised comments as the starting point for discussion. (20 minutes)

Tip

Set a framework for engagement at the start of your workshop. This can be a simple slide that sets the tone for equal, inclusive participation with a few principles or guidelines, for example: “All perspectives are welcome” and “Let’s make sure everyone has a chance to speak.”

Adaptation

Sticky notes and sticky dot voting can take place in person or online using a digital whiteboard such as Padlet, Miro or Mural. [Check the Miro templates that ENJOI prepared.](#)

- 5. Prioritising principles:** Participants took the elements that the public identified in response to the question “what made your example of science communication work well” and again, prioritised them using sticky dots. We opened up another short discussion around the outcomes. (10 minutes)
- 6. Break** (5-15 minutes).
- 7. Brainstorm and discussion:** Looking at the outcomes of the citizen consultation and thinking of their own experience, we asked participants to brainstorm on what they felt should be the desired principles of outstanding open science communication. They had three minutes to write sticky notes, one principle per sticky note. Then they presented their ideas and we clustered the common ideas. We discussed the groupings and gave titles to the clusters. (45 minutes)
- 8. Prioritisation of principles:** participants voted on the cluster titles with 3 sticky dots each to indicate what principles we should prioritise. (5 minutes)
- 9. Final discussion and wrap-up:** We discussed the outcomes and explained the next steps before thanking participants and closing. (10 minutes)

Tip

The outcomes can be posted online to allow further discussion, setting a deadline for the closure of the discussion and implementing a final prioritisation to achieve consensus.

Read more about the detailed steps in our ENJOI reports [Co-designing innovative multi-stakeholder engagement](#) and our [Report on the ENJOI Engagement Workshops](#)

C. ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOP MODULE 2: IDENTIFYING STANDARDS

Adaptation

In Portugal, the scenarios were not used. Instead participants discussed examples from their own work and experience in order to shape the standards. This adaptation worked particularly well in the context.

Tip

More ideas for warm-up activities can be found in the [SessionLab library](#).

Tip

To save time, this activity could be done online before the workshop.

The second workshop module of the co-creation process brings together the same group to envision ideal outcomes of open science communication scenarios. It aims to build on these scenarios to collectively identify standards that should be achieved within each principle established in the previous module.

We used **scenarios** based on good practices collected in the project: fictitious situations, inspired by real examples, where science journalism or science communication is being produced by professionals and where the ENJOI standards and principles could be applied. [See the four ENJOI scenarios here.](#)

There were eight key steps to the workshop:

- 1. Welcome:** We welcomed participants, explaining the objectives, detailing the agenda and giving practical, logistical or technical guidelines. (5 minutes)
- 2. Warm-up activity** to align on the notion of standards in science communication and help participants get to know each other. Participants took a pen and paper each and had ten seconds to draw an image that represents a word. Then they hold up their drawing so everyone can see. The first word was “success.” Then “communication”. Then “open.” Then “standard”. (10 minutes).
- 3. Presentation of scenarios:** Participants were presented with the four science communication [scenarios](#). (10 minutes)
- 4. Envisioning ideal outcomes:** Participants worked in three to four groups of 4-6 people each. Each group took one scenario and envisioned ideal outcomes of each scenario. What would be the impact of this activity if this science communication format was perfectly successful: in terms of the impact on the individual, on research, on society, for example? They had two minutes to brainstorm on sticky notes, five minutes to post their responses onto a poster, read each other’s responses, and cluster where appropriate. Participants voted to identify common elements of their ideal outcomes. (15 minutes)

Tip

Think about how many sticky dots you want to give each participant for the prioritisation. Fewer dots goes faster, whereas more dots means a more thorough exercise.

5. **Break** (5-15 minutes).
6. **Brainstorming standards:** Back in the groups, for each of the principles identified in Workshop 1, participants made a new poster and brainstormed the standards that would need to be met in this scenario to achieve their collective ideal outcome. They had five minutes to brainstorm standards individually, ten minutes to read out and explain the standards to the group, and twenty minutes discussion. These standards were voted and prioritised within the groups. (40 minutes)
7. **Clustering standards:** In plenary, each group presented their standards. There was a chance for discussion to clarify. (20 minutes)
8. **Final discussion:** This focused on what standards were missing under each principle. We discussed the outcomes and explained the next steps before thanking participants and closing. (15 minutes)

Read more about the detailed steps in our ENJOI reports [Co-designing innovative multi-stakeholder engagement](#) and our [Report on the ENJOI Engagement Workshops](#)

D. ENGAGEMENT WORKSHOP MODULE 3: DEFINING INDICATORS AND TOOLS

The third workshop module of the co-creation process brought together the same group to finalise the set of standards for outstanding open science communication co-created in previous workshops, collectively identifying indicators for each standard. It also contained an ideation session to define tools that could support a range of stakeholders in applying these SPIs.

There were nine key steps:

1. **Welcome:** We welcomed participants, explaining the objectives, detailing the agenda and giving practical, logistical or technical guidelines. (5 minutes)
2. **Warm-up activity** to align on the notion of indicators in science communication. Online, participants played a word association game in the chat: the facilitator types a word and the participants type the first word that comes to mind. Ideas for prompts: Journalist. Ethics. Fairness. Evaluation. Measurement. Indicator. (10 minutes).
3. **Brainstorming indicators:** Breakout groups were formed and each group was assigned a set of standards from the previous workshop, dividing the standards among the groups. In the breakout groups, they had five minutes to brainstorm what indicators could be used. How could each of the standards be measured? These indicators could apply broadly or could apply to specific formats. They then had ten minutes to read out each person's indicators and explain to the group, and twenty minutes discussion. These indicators were voted and prioritised within the groups. (40 minutes total).
4. **Break** (5-15 minutes)
5. **Presentation of tool ideation session:** Participants were introduced to the idea of tools to accompany these principles, standards and indicators. (5 minutes).

Tip

Keep a spare warm-up or energiser activity on hand during your workshops in case the energy in the group is low. Ideas can be found on [SessionLab](#).

Tip

Ideation is a technique developed in the field of design thinking. [Mural](#) has a range of tools that can be used online.

Tip

In ENJOI's Portuguese engagement workshop, this process was particularly creative, because they actually drew their prototypes. Pens, pencils, printable icons with multiple images, post-its, etc. were used to develop the tools.

6. **Whole group brainstorm:** Participants brainstormed to answer the question “what tool would help me implement these principles, standards and indicators?”. One idea per sticky note, two minutes to brainstorm. Participants posted their own two favourite ideas on the wall and had five minutes to read other ideas. Then, participants received three sticky dots and were asked to vote to prioritise tools that they thought would be useful for multiple stakeholders. The two highest-voted concepts were announced. (10 minutes)
7. **Ideation on two concepts:** The group split in two, three or four, and each group worked to develop one of the two highest-voted concepts. The groups collectively made posters to define: Who should this tool be aimed at? What are its objectives? What content and format should it include? Who can support its development? (30 minutes)
8. **Poster time:** The groups had time to read each other's posters. They added sticky notes with comments and feedback. (5 minutes)
9. **Final discussion and wrap-up:** We opened up the conversation around any final points that came up and explained the next steps before thanking participants and closing. (10 minutes)

Read more about the detailed steps in our ENJOI reports [Co-designing innovative multi-stakeholder engagement](#) and our [Report on the ENJOI Engagement Workshops](#). Read here what we did in [Italy](#), [Belgium](#), [Spain](#), and [Portugal](#). Or watch our video about the [Italian EW](#).

E. EUROPEAN CONSENSUS WORKSHOP

Our ENJOI European Consensus Workshop brought together the ENJOI consortium to collate the outcomes of the national Engagement Workshops at European level, building consensus around a European set of ENJOI SPIs for outstanding open science journalism and science communication.

It took place as a 2-hour online workshop on Zoom, using Miro, and had 10 key steps:

- 1. Welcome:** We welcomed participants, explained the objectives of the workshop and detailed the agenda.
- 2. Warm-up activity** where we shared highlights from the national co-creation processes. (10 minutes)
- 3. Presentation** of the European common national principles, standards and indicators. This presentation highlighted the common set of SPIs while also noting any key differences from country to country. (15 minutes)
- 4. First responses:** Participants were asked to comment on what struck them about the outcomes: are any of the results surprising? Did they feel anything was missing or underrepresented? This was done in Miro, with a voting session to prioritise comments. (5 minutes)
- 5. Discussion:** The facilitator raised the comments for discussion, starting with the highest-prioritised. Participants addressed the discussion points raised. (25 minutes)
- 6. “Unconference” topic selection:** Based on the highest-prioritised comments, the facilitator proposed 2 topics for main areas to be worked on and sought consensus in the group (5 minutes).
- 7. Break** (5 minutes)

Tip

Miro has some [templates for warm-ups](#) that can enliven online sessions.

Adaptation

Miro has a quick [voting tool](#) that makes for easy prioritisation online.

Tip

“[Unconference](#)” is a format that empowers participants to co-create the agenda.

8. Breakout groups: Participants split into breakout groups, one for each of the main areas to be worked on, to make recommendations for changes to the consensus. (25 minutes)

9. Presentation of outcomes: Participants from each group shared the main recommendations from their discussion. (15 minutes)

10. Overall discussion and finalisation. (10 minutes)

Read more about the detailed steps in our ENJOI reports [Co-designing innovative multi-stakeholder engagement](#) and our [Report on the ENJOI Engagement Workshops](#)

F. LABS

The ENJOI Labs were an opportunity to bring the ENJOI SPIs of outstanding open science communication to a new audience, to test out and refine them, with a focus on ensuring their practical applicability. It also contains a further ideation session to define tools that could support a range of stakeholders in applying these SPIs. In ENJOI, we chose to organise one Lab per stakeholder group: journalists, researchers, policy and public.

They were held either online or in-person, with participants receiving the ENJOI European SPI document as a pre-read, translated into the local language(s). The Labs had 11 key steps:

- 1. Welcome:** We welcomed participants, explaining the objectives, detailing the agenda and giving practical, logistical or technical guidelines. (5 minutes)
- 2. Warm-up activity** to align on the notion of outstanding open science journalism and science communication (10 minutes).
- 3. Presentation** of ENJOI European SPIs. (10 minutes)
- 4. Test exercise:** Participants worked in small groups to collectively plan a real science communication activity based on their current work. They were tasked with making a poster to identify how they would apply the SPIs to their work. What would they find useful? (20 minutes)
- 5. Brainstorming recommendations:** Within the small groups, there was a collective brainstorm of recommendations for how the SPIs could be improved (5 minutes to brainstorm ideas) followed by a prioritisation exercise (5 minutes to read each other's ideas and vote with sticky dots) to highlight the main recommendations. (15 minutes)
- 6. Break** (5 minutes)

Adaptation

In some Labs, the “test exercise” step was skipped or replaced with a discussion: for example, in Portugal the researchers reviewed the SPIs and discussed how they could contribute.

Tip

Adapt your activities to the cultural context. In the Belgian lab, online, the [Silent Brainstorm](#) technique worked well to ensure participants all had their say on the SPIs. In the Italian lab, with journalists who were keen to talk, this technique was less successful!

7. Presentation of tool ideation session: Just as in the engagement workshops, participants were introduced to the idea of tools to accompany these principles, standards and indicators. (5 minutes).

8. Whole group brainstorm: Participants brainstormed to answer the question “what tool would help me implement these principles, standards and indicators?”. One idea per sticky note, two minutes to brainstorm. Participants posted their own two favourite ideas on the wall and had five minutes to read other ideas. Then, participants received three sticky dots and were asked to vote to prioritise tools that they thought would be useful for multiple stakeholders. The two highest-voted concepts were announced. (10 minutes)

9. Ideation on two concepts: The group split in two and each group worked to develop one of the two highest-voted concepts. The groups collectively made posters to define: Who should this tool be aimed at? What are its objectives? What content and format should it include? Who can support its development? (30 minutes)

10. Poster time: The groups had time to read each other's posters. They added sticky notes with comments and feedback. (5 minutes)

11. Final discussion and wrap-up: We opened up the conversation around any final points that came up and explained the next steps before thanking participants and closing. (10 minutes)

Read more about the detailed steps in our ENJOI reports Co-designing innovative multi-stakeholder engagement and our Report on the ENJOI Labs, or watch our video about the Italian Lab [here](#).

LEARNINGS FROM ENJOI

1. Co-create your format to help ensure all participants have their say

In ENJOI, our co-creation methodology itself was co-created, through a series of workshops with partners from different backgrounds and profiles. Our evaluation suggested that the format of the Engagement Workshops and Labs made it easier for participants to contribute and that all voices could be heard, regardless of the profile of the participant.

2. Use diversity to enrich the process

Our evaluation showed that the opportunity for science communication professionals of different backgrounds (researchers, practitioners and journalists) to meet and exchange views around science communication was seen as a particularly valuable opportunity - particularly the presence of groups that are usually underrepresented. Take this into account in your mapping, and take advantage of this diversity in your format.

3. Keep the timing tight

Participants often don't have time to commit to long co-creation sessions. In ENJOI, participants noted that the format ensured that participants covered a lot of ground and that this had a positive effects on their groups' mood and interest levels.

4. Ensure alignment on the topic

In ENJOI we had to engage participants in a complex topic: standards, principles and indicators for science communication. Our evaluation showed that in some cases we should have been more careful to check all participants understood what we meant. This could be done ahead of each workshop or through some additional activities online.

5. Use concrete examples

Co-creation can be an abstract process. Our evaluation showed that sometimes the approach tended to focus on discussion around concepts that were too theoretical. Think about your activities ahead of time and ask yourself: how could these be better rooted in real-life examples?

6. Mix large and small group discussion

The structure of your format defined by the methodological approach is crucial. By mixing large and small group work, you can help ensure participants get to know each other, and have time for reflection as well as discussion.

7. Make time for sharing and networking

Your participants are only human! They will enjoy getting to know each other. In ENJOI, the opportunities to exchange with others was a motivating factor in their participation that they valued and the connections they made sparked contacts and initiatives beyond the workshop.

8. Keep in touch

An unexpected side-effect of the ENJOI process was the enthusiasm. Participants wanted to hear more about what happened with the outcomes. In your process, think about tools and platforms you can use to keep your group informed and engaged.

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